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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Where Theory Meets Practice: My Field Study Journey

Before, I thought education was mostly about theories, lesson plans, and everything written in books inside the classroom. However, my Field Study experience made me realize that learning becomes more real and meaningful when you actually see it happening. It connected what I learned from textbooks to what truly goes on in a classroom, the challenges, the adjustments, and the small but rewarding moments of teaching.

One thing that really stood out to me was how different each learner is. No two students are the same. Some were very active and confident in answering, while others stayed quiet and needed more time and encouragement. Seeing this made me realize how important the teacher's role is in ensuring everyone is included. Teaching is not just following one method; it is about adjusting, being flexible, and finding ways to reach every student.

I also noticed how the teacher managed the class. It was not about being strict or making students feel afraid. Instead, it was about respect, patience, and consistency. The teacher used fun activities, gave clear instructions, and positively encouraged students. It showed me that discipline works best when students feel understood, not controlled. During my field study, I am the one handling the learners. This was because my cooperating teacher's child was dying, so she took a short break. The principal asked me if I was willing to handle the learners in grade 2. Without hesitation, I agreed. However, we agreed that I would handle only the 5 learners, and the rest would have a modular class. The 5 learners I will handle are DepEd Aral Program-qualified learners who are having difficulty reading. So, at that time we used to do their daily routine, and after that we would read some words I wrote on the board, and then I gave each learner one story. I will call them one by one to assess their reading. To ease their boredom, I will give them time to play, and after that, we will return to what we have been doing.

Another thing that touched me was the emotional side of teaching. The teacher did not just focus on lessons but also showed care for the students. Simple things like giving praise or checking in made a big difference in how they participated and how they felt about themselves. That made me realize that teaching is not just about knowledge, it is also about the heart. The way they participate in class, we should praise them and offer a kind word to encourage them and boost their confidence.

This experience made me reflect on myself as a future teacher. I realized that being an educator is not easy. It requires patience, understanding, creativity, and dedication. It also challenged me to keep improving so I can meet the needs of different learners and create a classroom where everyone feels important.

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During the time I handled the learners, many staff members were present. First, way back when I was in school at Palompon Institute of Technology Tabango Campus (PIT-TC), our instructor always said that a teacher requires more patience, especially when dealing with their learners, and one thing they always said is that there are some situations in which learners may poop. As a teacher, it is your obligation to care for your learners, as I have experienced during my field study. It was a normal day, and as we went about our daily routine, one of my learners shouted that he was at the CR at that time. He said, "Teacher, there is poop in the bowl, and it smells so bad" at first, I laughed maybe that learner is joking not until other learners go check the CR and they said the same way, so I checked the CR so as their guidance that time so I obliged to plush the poop so that they can use again the CR.

In the end, my Field Study experience was eye-opening and meaningful. It made me appreciate teaching even more and helped me see clearly the kind of teacher I want to become: someone who not only teaches lessons but also inspires, supports, and makes a difference in students' lives.